

Solution behaviour of mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) involving penicillin group drugs and sulfur containing ligands under physiological conditions

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Manuscript received 22 March 2000, accepted 23 April 2000

Analysis of the pH-titration data obtained in aqueous perchlorate medium at 37° and $I = 0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄) for Ni^{II}-A-B mixed ligand systems [A = 6apa or amp; B = cys, smc, pen or cya] shows the presence of mixed ligand complex species NiABH, NiAB and/or NiAH₁B in addition to various binary species due to ligands A and B. The $\text{p}K_{\text{NiABH}}^{\text{II}}$ values obtained in all these systems are close to each other, indicating the site of protonation in the NiABH species to be with ligand A. In the NiAB type of complexes, coordination of the ligand A results in the formation of a five-membered ring. In the NiAH₁B species in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-B systems, deprotonated AH₁ ligand binds the metal in a tridentate manner. In all the mixed ligand complexes, cys, smc, pen and cya(B) ligands are bidentate. The statistical parameter $\Delta \log K$ calculated indicates preferential formation and enhanced stability for the mixed ligand complexes relative to the binary one.

Biological metal ions play a key role in the structural organisation and activation of enzymes¹. Nickel activates many enzymes and stabilises RNA and DNA against thermal denaturation². Considering that most reactions in which antibiotic drugs participate are also dependent on metal ions³, it is rather surprising to find that the metal ion binding properties of penicillin group of drugs have hardly been investigated. There are few reports⁴ on systematic investigations of mixed ligand complexes involving S-containing ligands such as L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid.

The aim of present investigation is to study the complex formation of Ni^{II} with 6-aminopenicillanic acid (6apa) and a commonly used form of penicillin, viz. α -D-(-) aminopenicillin (ampicillin) in presence of biologically important sulfur containing ligands, viz. L-cysteine, S-methylcysteine (smc), D-penicillamine (pen) or L-cysteic acid (cya) under physiological conditions to throw light upon the molecular mechanisms of action of these drugs and the effect of the metal ion. The complex equilibria of both L-cysteine, and D-penicillamine are determined by the mercaptosulfur atom which is soft in character⁵. Through the mercapto group, these compounds participate in both redox and acid-base reactions⁶. The quantitatively important path way of L-cysteine metabolism is the oxidation to L-cysteic acid. A study of the interaction of Cu^{II} with L-cysteine and D-penicillamine is highly complicated because complex formation and redox reactions takes place simultaneously⁷. A deeper understanding of this type of chemical reactions

require the extension of investigation to complexes of other transition metal ions such as Ni^{II} which is not susceptible to redox reactions. By potentiometric pH-titrations we have now determined the stability of the mixed ligand complexes and evaluated the solution behaviour.

Results and Discussion

Eight mixed ligand complex systems, namely, Ni^{II}-6apa/amp(A)-cys, smc, pen and cya(B) are discussed in this section (Tables 2 and 3). The Ni^{II}-6apa(A)-cys, smc, pen and cya(B) systems show the presence of two types of mixed ligand complexes, viz. NiABH and NiAB while in the corresponding Ni^{II}-amp(A)-B systems NiAH₁B species in addition to the above species have been detected.

Stability and structure of NiAB type of mixed ligand complex species : The $\log K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiB}} (= \log \beta_{\text{NiAB}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiB}})$ values obtained in the title systems (Table 2) compare favorably with the $\log K_1$ value obtained for the NiA 6apa/amp binary species (Table 1), where the 6apa ligand binds Ni^{II} through 6-aminonitrogen and 7-carbonyl oxygen atoms⁸, while amp ligand binds Ni^{II} through amino nitrogen and amide oxygen atoms⁹. Hence, it can be concluded that in the NiAB mixed ligand complex species also, the 6apa/amp ligands bind the metal ion in a similar way. Again, the $\log K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiA}} (= \log \beta_{\text{NiAB}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiA}})$ values obtained in the Ni^{II}-6apa/amp(A)-cys, smc, pen and cya(B) mixed ligand complex systems bear favorable comparison with the respective $\log K_1$ values (Table 1) obtained in the

Ni^{II}-cys, smc, pen and cya(B) systems after taking into account of statistical factors. This demonstrates that the secondary ligands(B) in the NiAB species bind the metal ion in the same way as in their binary species, i.e. the cys and pen ligands bind the metal through the mercapto and primary amino groups, while smc and cya bind the metal ion in a glycine-like mode⁸.

Table 1. Stability constants for the proton and parent binary complexes of Ni^{II} with 6apa, amp, cya, cys, smc and pen(B)

Temp. = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm ⁻³ (NaClO ₄)	apa ^a	amp ^b	cys ^c	smc ^c	pen ^c	cya ^c
log β _{HAB}	4.69(1)	6.83(2)	10.31(2)	8.23(2)	10.89(1)	8.41(1)
log β _{H₂B}	7.02(3)	9.72(5)	18.53(7)	10.99(4)	18.89(3)	10.56(4)
log β _{HAB}	-	-	19.93(8)	-	20.80(9)	-
log β _{NiBH}	7.37(2)	8.89(9)	-	11.24(2)	-	-
log β _{NiB}	3.27(2)	3.58(6)	9.14(9)	5.72(3)	11.50(3)	5.93(4)
log β _{NiB₂H}	9.61(5)	-	25.86(9)	-	-	-
log β _{NiB₂}	-	-	20.21(5)	11.04(2)	23.41(1)	10.53(6)
log β _{NiAH₋₁}	-	-4.64(8)	-	-	-	-
pK _{NiBH} ^H	4.10	5.31	-	5.52	-	-
pK _{NiB₂H} ^H	-	-	5.65	-	-	-
log K _{NiB₂} ^{NiB}	-	-	5.32	11.91	4.60	11.07
log P	-	-	-	3.01	-	-

^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 9. ^cRef. 7.

The log β_{NiAB} value obtained in the Ni^{II}-6apa(A)-smc(B) mixed ligand complex system (9.29) bears favorable comparison with that in the Ni^{II}-6apa(A)-cya(B) system (9.03). Also, the log β_{NiAB} value obtained in the Ni^{II}-6apa(A)-smc(B) mixed ligand complex system is comparable with that in the Ni^{II}-6apa(A)-glycine(B) system (9.77)¹⁰. This supports the glycine like-mode of coordination of smc and cya in the Ni^{II}-6apa(A)-smc/cya(B) mixed ligand complex systems. Thus, the NiAB species in all these mixed ligand complex systems would contain two 5-membered chelate rings. The Δ log K_{NiAB} values obtained in these systems are more positive compared to the statistical values¹¹ indicating marked stabilization of the mixed ligand complex species.

Stability and structure of NiABH type of mixed ligand complex species: The NiABH type of species has been detected in all the title mixed ligand complex systems and their formation has been found to be favored in the pH range 4.0–5.5. With regard to the site of protonation in these NiABH species, it seems that the proton is attached to the primary ligand A, possibly to its terminal amino group as in the case with NiAH (H + 6apa or amp) complexes. This would become apparent by noting that the pK_{NiABH}^H values (Table 2) are comparable to each other in all these systems. In the Ni^{II}-6apa/amp(A) systems protonated binary species were detected^{8,9} while except in the Ni^{II}-smc(B) no protonated species were found⁷. The

trend that the log K_{Ni(AH)B}^{NiAH} values obtained in these systems bearing favorable comparison with the log K₁ values in the Ni-B systems indicates that the ligands B bind Ni^{II} in a bidentate manner similar to their binding in the respective binary species. Thus in the NiABH type of species in these systems the protonated ligand A binds the metal ion in a monodentate manner and the ligands B would bind in a bidentate manner.

The Δ log K_{NiABH} (= log β_{NiABH} - log β_{NiAH} - log β_{NiB}) values computed are more positive compared to the statistical values¹¹ suggesting that the NiABH type of species are markedly stabilized. In all these systems appreciable amount of the total metal ion has been found to be present in the form of NiABH species, which reflects the conclusions arrived at from the statistical parameter, Δ log K (Tables 2 and 3). In all these systems NiAH/NiB binary species is present in appreciable amounts at low pH. As pH increases the concentration of this species decreases and the concentration of the NiABH type of species becomes appreciable.

Table 2. Stability constants for the Ni^{II}-6apa(A)-cys, smc, pen and cya(B) mixed ligand complex systems

Temp. = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm ⁻³ (NaClO ₄)	cys	smc	pen	cya
log β _{NiABH}	18.84(6)	14.59(5)	20.02(2)	14.13(3)
log β _{NiAB}	13.12(4)	9.29(3)	15.25(1)	9.03(7)
pK _{NiABH} ^H	5.36	5.30	4.77	5.10
log K _{NiABH} ^{NiAH}	11.11	7.22	12.65	6.76
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiA}	9.85	6.02	11.98	5.76
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiB}	3.98	3.57	3.75	3.10
Δ log K _{NiABH}	1.97	1.50	1.15	0.83
Δ log K _{NiAB}	0.71	0.30	0.48	-0.17

Table 3. Stability constants for the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-cys, smc, pen and cya(B) mixed ligand complex systems

Temp. = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm ⁻³ (NaClO ₄)	cys	smc	pen	cya
log β _{NiABH}	18.17(3)	14.49(8)	20.49(9)	14.36(2)
log β _{NiAB}	13.54(8)	9.81(1)	15.71(3)	9.49(6)
log β _{NiAH₋₁B}	4.58(9)	1.32(9)	6.99(8)	1.27(8)
pK _{NiAH₋₁B} ^H	8.96	8.49	8.72	8.22
pK _{NiABH} ^H	4.63	4.68	4.78	4.87
log K _{NiABH} ^{NiAH}	9.28	5.60	11.60	5.47
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiA}	9.96	6.23	12.13	5.91
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiB}	4.40	4.09	4.21	3.56
log K _{NiAH₋₁B} ^{NiAH}	9.22	5.96	11.63	5.91
Δ log K _{NiABH}	0.14	-0.12	0.10	-0.46
Δ log K _{NiAB}	0.82	0.51	0.63	-0.02
Δ log K _{NiAH₋₁B}	0.08	0.24	0.13	-0.02

Stability and structure of NiAH₋₁B type of mixed ligand complex species: The NiAH₋₁B type of species has been

found to be present only in the amp(A) systems and to be favored above pH 6.5. Only in the Ni^{II}-amp(A) binary system, the deprotonated binary species of the type NiAH₁ has been identified⁹. The $pK_{\text{NiAH}_1}^{\text{H}}$ values obtained are comparable to each other. Hence, in the NiAH₁B type of species it can be expected that the deprotonation is from the ligand A. The $\log K_{\text{NiAH}_1}^{\text{NiAH}_1, \text{B}}$ ($= \log \beta_{\text{NiAH}_1, \text{B}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiAH}_1}$) values computed in all these systems bear favorable comparison with the $\log K_1$ values obtained in the corresponding Ni-B binary systems.

Thus, in the NiAH₁B species in these systems, the ligands AH₁ and B bind the metal ion in a similar way as in the corresponding binary species, i.e. in the NiAH₁B species in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-cys, smc, pen and cya(B) systems, a coordination number of five can be expected due to the tridentate coordination of amp(A) and bidentate coordination of the respective secondary ligands(B). Of course, the sixth position would be completed by a water molecule. The $\Delta \log K_{\text{NiAH}_1}^{\text{NiAH}_1, \text{B}}$ ($= \log \beta_{\text{NiAH}_1, \text{B}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiAH}_1} - \log \beta_{\text{NiB}}$) values obtained in all these systems are positive compared to the statistical values showing enhanced stabilities for the NiAH₁B mixed ligand complexes compared to the NiAH₁ and NiB binary species.

Experimental

All the ligands used were obtained from Fluka AG. The method of preparation of all the reagents and other experimental details have been described earlier¹². The cys ligand used was in the mono-protonated form. A constant ionic strength of 0.15 mol dm⁻³ was maintained by the addition of sodium perchlorate. The stability constants for the mixed ligand complex systems were computed with the aid of the MINQUAD 75 computer program¹³ on a HCL Magnum II 68030 twin processor minicomputer. During the computation of mixed ligand complex stability, the stability constant for the binary complexes of Ni^{II} with the ligands

A and B estimated⁹ under identical conditions (Table 1) were treated as non-refinable parameters.

References

1. Metal Ions in Biological Systems, eds. A. Sigel and H. Sigel, M. Dekker, New York, 1971-1997, Vols. 1-34.
2. J. M. Mortil, M. J. Martinez Ferriz, H. R. Jimenez, A. Domercq, J. Castells and J. Salgado, *J. Inorg. Biochem.* 1992, **45**, 231. K. D. Karlin and Z. Tsvetkov, *Bioinorganic Chemistry*, Chapman Hall, New York, 1993.
3. J. J. R. Frausto da Silva and R. J. P. Williams, *The Biological Chemistry of the Elements*, Clarendon, Oxford, 1991. A. Sigel and H. Sigel, *Hand Book on Toxicity of Inorganic Compounds*, 3rd ed., M. Dekker, New York, 1997. M. Glicen, P. Icheveld, D. Devos and R. Willim, *Metal based Antitumor Drugs*, Plenum Pub. House, Tel Aviv, 1997, Vol. 2.
4. I. Sovigo, A. Geigley, B. Harman and F. Kiss, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* 1979, **41**, 1629. A. Kivali and G. Berthoin, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.* 1980, 2374. P. R. Reddy, K. Sudhakar and T. I. Adharam, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A* 1991, **30**, 522. A. I. Mitchell, R. M. Smith and R. J. Motekaitis, National Institute of Science and Technology (NIST) Critical Stability Constants of Metal Complexes Database, NIST Standard Reference Database 46, Gaithersburg, 1993.
5. R. G. Pearson, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 1990, **100**, 403.
6. J. E. Huheey, E. A. Keiter and R. L. Keiter, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, Collins, New York, 1993.
7. M. S. Nair, P. T. Arasu, M. S. Pillai and C. Natunjan, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.* 1993, 917.
8. M. S. Nair and M. A. Neelakantan, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A* 1999, **38**, 194.
9. M. S. Nair and M. A. Neelakantan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 2000, **77**, 23.
10. G. N. Mukherjee and T. K. Gosh, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A* 1992, **30**, 478.
11. H. Sigel in *IUPAC Coordination Chemistry 20*, ed. D. Bancroft, Pergamon, Oxford, 1980.
12. M. S. Nair, P. T. Arasu, M. S. Pillai and C. Natunjan, *Talanta* 1993, **40**, 1411. *Transition Met. Chem.* 1995, 917. M. S. Nair, J. P. Anbarasi, P. T. Arasu and M. A. Neelakantan, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A* 1999, **38**, 166.
13. P. Gans, A. Vacca and A. Sabatini, *Inorg. Chim. Acta* 1976, **18**, 237.